

Homopolar Rotor Slot Harmonics for Inter-Turn Fault Detection in Induction Motors

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Abstract—Stator faults detection under normal operation is one of the most important open problems in Induction Motors (IMs): they start as Inter-Turn Faults (ITFs) and rapidly evolve into catastrophic failures, being one of the major causes of shutdown. Hence, continuous monitoring is essential for early detection. Regarding this, line current analysis is preferred due to ease of equipment installation. In this paper, a new ITF indicator is proposed: amplitude of the homopolar Rotor Slot Harmonics (RSHs); those that form a homopolar system in a symmetrical machine. These harmonics are proven as always highly sensitive, opposite to previously used RSHs, which appear as sensitive or completely insensitive, depending on the motor analyzed. It is shown how ITF detection can be reliably solved using homopolar RSHs: they dramatically rise under early ITFs. To achieve generality, a theoretical analysis is conducted to deduce which are these RSHs as a function of the number of bars per pole pairs of the IM. Moreover, the proposed approach automatically selects and detects these harmonics, and ensures robustness against load, eccentricity and voltage unbalance variations. Efficacy of this approach is confirmed through finite element simulations of three IMs covering all cases and laboratory tests.

Index Terms—Condition monitoring, fault diagnosis, induction motors, interturn faults, motor current signature analysis (MCSA).

NOMENCLATURE

IM/s	Induction Motor/s.
ITF/s	Inter-Turn Fault/s.
RSH/s	Rotor Slot Harmonic/s.
PSH/s	Principal Slot Harmonic/s.
SWFH/s	Stator Winding Fault Harmonic/s.
SFW/s	Spatial Flux Wave/s.
f_{RSH}	RSH frequency.
f_0	Supply fundamental frequency.
k	Natural number (1, 2, 3...).
p	Number of pole pairs.
R	Number of rotor rotor bars/slots.
s	Slip.
m_s	Number of stator phases.
ν	Order of a time harmonic in the stator current (positive odd number).
ω_ν	Angular frequency of a time harmonic.
h_s	Relative order of a stator's harmonic SFW (positive odd number).

$\frac{s, sy_s}{\Phi_{h_s}^{s, sy_s}}$	Stator reference system. Harmonic yoke-flux space phasor generated by the stator currents. = 1 (positive sequence subsystem) or = -1 (negative sequence subsystems).
g	Natural number (1, 2, 3...).
n	Time.
t	= 1, 2, ..., R.
y, r	Currents induced in each rotor bar due to the stator's fundamental SFW.
$i_{y,r}^{h_s=1}$	Rotor bar current amplitude.
I_R	Rotor mechanical speed.
Ω_R	Relative order of a rotor's harmonic SFW (positive odd number).
h_r	Harmonic yoke-flux space phasor generated by the rotor currents. = 1, 2, ..., m_s .
$\overrightarrow{\Phi_{h_r}^{s, sy_s}}$	Currents induced in each stator phase due to the rotor's harmonic SFWs.
x, s	Stator current amplitude.
$i_{x,s}^{h_r}$	Time harmonic of f_0 .
I_s	Order of a time harmonic in the stator current (positive odd number) considering the sign in (1).
f_ν	Voltage Unbalance Index.
ν_{sign}	Current Unbalance Index.
VUI	Simulated induction motors.
CUI	Shorted Turn/s.
M1, M2, M3	Homopolar RSHs of negative and positive ν_{sign} in Table V.
ST/s	Full and no-load frequency of homopolar RSHs in Table V.
RSH_1, RSH_2	Full and no-load amplitude of homopolar RSHs at healthy state in Table V.
f_{FL}, f_{NL}	Full and no-load amplitude of homopolar RSHs at faulty state in Table V.
$A_{FL,H}, A_{NL,H}$	Voltage Unbalance.
$A_{FL,F}, A_{NL,F}$	Mixed Eccentricity.
VU	Taps in phase R of the experimental motor.
ME	Switch position in experimental setup.
R, R_1, R_2, R_3	Contact resistance.
$A, A_0, A_1 \dots$	
R_c	

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I. INTRODUCTION

Among the different faults that can occur in an Induction Motor (IM), stator faults are one of the most important to detect: they represent 30 and 66% of all reported failures in low and medium-to-high voltage IMs respectively [1]. At their initial stages, stator faults appear as Inter-Turn Faults (ITF),

which eventually evolve into catastrophic failures: phase-to-phase or phase-to-ground short-circuits [2]. This evolution is faster than in other typical faults (e.g., eccentricity or broken bars). Therefore, it is crucial to detect a stator fault as early as possible, i.e. when it is still an ITF of low severity (low short-circuit current).

Several methodologies have been proposed to detect ITFs [3]. In this regard, surge test [4] and Partial Discharge test [5] may detect turn-to-turn insulation problems. Nevertheless, the first must be performed offline, while the latter needs additional equipment installed at the motor terminals [3]. Another approach is the stator winding temperature monitoring, either through a sensor [6] or by estimation techniques [7], [8]. However, false tripping is a common issue with temperature sensors [7], while estimation techniques require the knowledge of machine parameters and/or the use of additional equipment to inject signals. In addition, it is not easy to determine if the temperature increase is due to a stator fault or a mechanical or load problem. Some interesting works propose Neural Networks (NN) and Machine Learning (ML) techniques on the acquired signals and parameters to classify between healthy, ITFs and other asymmetries of the machine, even determining the fault severity [9], [10], [11]. However, AI-driven methods show as main drawback the reliance on high-quality, unbiased training data to perform effectively. Moreover, most of them lack Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI), which hinders understanding of their decision-making processes and creates a tradeoff between accuracy/performance and explainability. Good results have also been reported with methods based on multi-sensors and fusion-based approaches that combine, for example, the use of vibration sensors [12], currents and voltages data [13] or thermal and magnetic measurements [14]. Finally, another on-line approach is to use as fault indicator the amplitude variation of certain harmonics in the spectrum of different signals. The most common are current [15]–[25] and flux [23], [26]–[28], but there also methodologies based on voltage [29], instantaneous power [30] and vibration [31].

The ITF rapidly evolves into a catastrophic failure, unlike eccentricities and rotor asymmetries [20]. Thus, a continuous monitoring approach must be taken to prompt the user about the appearance of the ITF as early as possible. Regarding this, the most suitable approach is one based on the current, since this quantity can be easily measured at the motor control cabinet. Conversely, other sensors, such as a flux, temperature, vibration sensors or coupling capacitors, must be installed at the motor location and run a power cable to the control panel, or alternatively, installing near the IM all the necessary elements to power the sensor, capture and send the signal to a server. This is especially difficult in certain applications: motors working in hazardous environments (e.g. explosive atmospheres), submerged (e.g., deep well pumping [20], [24]), etc. Hence, monitoring of line current indicators becomes an attractive choice since it is of general application and, if based on ITF-related harmonics monitoring, it greatly simplifies the technology and analysis needed.

Regarding the current, three types of harmonics have been proposed as fault indicators: the third harmonic of the fundamental frequency [15]–[17], the Stator Winding Fault Har-

monics (SWFHs) [18]–[21] and the Rotor Slot Harmonics (RSHs) [15], [21]–[25]. The third harmonic tends to have an already high amplitude in healthy state due to the inherent asymmetries [32], and therefore, it shows less sensitivity to the ITF at its very initial stages [23]. SWFHs require the existence of additional asymmetries in the machine (e.g., eccentricity) to appear in the line current [21]. Conversely, every IM can produce at least some groups of RSHs [33], even in the case of perfectly symmetrical machine, since they are caused by the discrete nature of rotor winding [34], and, additionally, they appear in a region of the spectrum that is less populated and with low noise-floor (due to greater distance to the fundamental component). Yet, to date, no results have been published as for which RSHs, among all the existent ones, should be used as ITF indicators for every type of motor

To properly review detection approaches based on RSHs, it should be remembered that RSHs frequency in a given motor operating at certain speed, depends on three factors (Section II, equation (1)): a natural number k , the sign \pm taken in their formula, and an odd number ν . When, $k = 1$ the RSHs are referred as Principal Slot Harmonics (PSHs). In [15] it is shown that, for the specific six-poles, 32 bars IM tested, PSHs associated to $[\pm, \nu = 1]$ increase in amplitude with the introduction of an ITF. However, it is not shown whether the amplitude of these harmonics continues to increase as the fault severity increases, since the tests are conducted only in healthy state and with a few shorted-turns. In [21], the PSHs associated to $[\pm, \nu = 1]$, $[+, \nu = 3]$ in a ten-poles, 90 bars IM and $[\pm, \nu = 1]$, $[+, \nu = 3, 5]$ in a two-poles, 40 bars IM are analyzed. For these particular IMs, it is observed that the PSH associated to $[+, \nu = 3]$ shows the best sensitivity and a continuous increasing behavior, while the rest show decreasing behavior or are insensitive to the fault. However, no explanation for these differences is provided. For the 4-poles, 28 bars IM analyzed in [22], it is observed that the PSH associated to $[-, \nu = 1]$ shows an increasing behavior with very low sensitivity at full load and a non-monotonic behavior at no load, while the PSH $[+, \nu = 1]$ shows high sensitivity when an ITF is introduced. In [23], PSHs linked to $[+, \nu = 1, 3]$ are studied under very low severity ITFs in a four-poles, 32 bars IM, showing them to be insensitive. In [24], it is proven that for a very particular machine (deep-well submersible motor), the PSHs that are absent in healthy state show the best correlation with the ITF, which are PSHs linked to $[\pm, \nu = 3]$ in the motor studied (two-poles and 30 bars). Finally, in [25], it is shown how the RSHs linked to $[k = 1, 2, +, \nu = 1]$ present in the space phasor modulus show a good correlation with the fault in a four-poles, 28 bars machine. A summary of this discussion can be found in Table I.

As can be seen, PSHs that are good ITF indicators for specific IMs, are bad for others, but no research gives an explanation, neither experimental, nor theoretical. Some works even claim that PSHs are insensitive to the ITF, at least under their case analyzed. Moreover, up to now, most works have focused their attention on PSHs, but do not give a solution for the motors that are not able to produce them (e.g., big machines, where bars are usually not skewed, and consequently rotors are designed with non-even number of rotor bars per

TABLE I
ROTOR SLOTS HARMONICS EXAMINED IN LITERATURE FOR ITF DETECTION

Reference	Motor characteristics	RSH/s examined	Sensitive to ITF
[15]	$p = 3, R = 32$	$[k = 1, \pm, \nu = 1]$	Both
[21]	$p = 5, R = 90$ $p = 1, R = 40$	$[k = 1, \pm, \nu = 1], [k = 1, +, \nu = 3]$ $[k = 1, \pm, \nu = 1], [k = 1, +, \nu = 3, 5]$	$[+, \nu = 3]$
[22]	$p = 2, R = 28$	$[k = 1, \pm, \nu = 1]$	$[k = 1, +, \nu = 1]$
[23]	$p = 2, R = 32$	$[k = 1, +, \nu = 1, 3]$	None
[24]	$p = 1, R = 30$	$[k = 1, \pm, \nu = 1, 3, 5]$	$[k = 1, \pm, \nu = 3]$
[25]	$p = 2, R = 28$	$[k = 1, 2, +, \nu = 1]$ (space phasor modulus)	Both

pole pair). Therefore, without a methodology to determine which RSHs must be monitored in every IM, they cannot be used as reliable ITF indicators in automatic and continuous monitoring systems. In addition, studies that present certain RSHs as ITF indicators miss the incorporation of an automatic speed estimation algorithm. This is a common problem in most works that use speed-dependent harmonics as fault indicators. However, this is an extremely important step, since in order to extract their amplitude, the frequency must be located first in the spectrum, which depends on the slip. In the case of RSHs, the extraction problem is even more difficult, since a method must also be provided to determine the parameter kR/p (usually unknown to motor owners), since the frequency also depends on it. Thus, conclusion extracted from previous works is that RSHs are not reliable ITF indicators, since there are no rules to determine which RSHs must be used in each IM (sometimes even claiming them insensitive to the ITF), and the extraction of their amplitude is not a trivial problem (no method is provided to determine the slip and kR/p).

The present work takes an important step forward in solving the problem of ITF detection using continuous monitoring methods of general application, by proposing a methodology that, for the first time, uses as fault indicators the homopolar RSHs (those that form a homopolar system in a symmetrical machine). As proven in the paper, homopolar RSHs (and not the already present in the line current of a symmetrical machine), experience a radical increase in amplitude when an ITF occurs in all IMs, thus giving rise to a very sensitive detection method. Since the homopolar RSHs are different depending on the motor considered (they are associated with different k and ν), a theoretical analysis is conducted to deduce which are these harmonics for any IM, regardless the combination of rotor bars and pole pairs) (Section II). Then, in Section III, a complete diagnosis approach is presented by proposing an ITF continuous monitoring method that includes the use of homopolar RSHs as fault indicators, the incorporation of an automatic slip estimation method that also provides the kR/p parameter needed to select and locate these harmonics, and the use of three auxiliary indicators to make the system robust against load changes, eccentricity and voltage unbalance. To apply this diagnosis scheme, only line currents and voltages must be recorded, thereby allowing general applicability. In Section IV, the theoretical analysis and validity of the fault detection approach is confirmed by means of finite element simulations, using the models of three real IMs and up to

27 simulations. Finally, in Section V, the methodology is validated in a real motor with different type of supplies and under different levels of ITF severity, load, eccentricity, voltage unbalance, and contact resistance, making a total of 40 validation experiments. The paper focuses its scope in 3-phase IMs under open-loop steady-state operation, which are the most common motors and operating conditions in industry.

Therefore, the main novelties and contributions of this paper with respect to previous works are:

- Theoretical and experimental proof of which are the RSHs sensitive to the ITF in every IM.
- Methodology to select them in every IM among all the existent RSHs as a function of kR/p .
- Incorporation of a specific speed estimation algorithm that allows obtaining both the slip and the parameter kR/p needed to reliably select and locate the RSHs that must be used as ITF indicators.
- Definition and incorporation of three auxiliary indicators that make the diagnostic system robust against load changes, the occurrence of eccentricity and voltage unbalance.

II. RSHS AS FAULT INDICATORS OF INTER-TURN FAULTS

Rotor Slot Harmonics (RSHs) are a series of well-known harmonics present in the stator current of an IM, whose frequencies are given by [35]:

$$f_{RSH} = \left[k \frac{R}{p} (1 - s) \pm \nu \right] f_0 \quad (1)$$

where $k \in \mathbb{N}$, p is the number of pole pairs, s the slip, ν is the order of the time harmonic present in the stator current (a positive odd number), f_0 the fundamental frequency of the supply voltage, and R the number of rotor bars.

As shown in this section, even though a motor can produce a certain group of RSHs (i.e. RSHs linked to the same k), not all the RSHs of that group are present in the line current of a symmetrical machine, since some of them form a homopolar system. However, when an ITF occurs in the stator winding, the symmetry of the machine is lost and its main flux is altered. As a consequence, the homopolar RSHs are no longer homopolar. More precisely, when the ITF occurs, two systems of RSHs coexist at the same frequency as those RSHs that form a homopolar system in the symmetrical machine: the original homopolar system and a new one that is non-homopolar and it is caused by the ITF. The homopolar system

cancels in the line current, while the non-homopolar does not, being this what enables the ITF detection in the line current. Therefore, in this paper, the term homopolar RSHs refers to: those RSHs form a homopolar system in a symmetrical machine, and those RSHs that appear in the line current at that same frequencies under an ITF.

As shown in Section IV, the homopolar RSHs shows a very high sensitivity to the fault. In healthy state, they have zero amplitude, while under any small ITF, they have a significant amplitude due to their appearance in the spectrum because of the loss of symmetry. On the contrary, the amplitude of those RSHs that already existed in the line current of the symmetrical machine barely varies, since they already had high amplitudes. Hence, the amplitude tracking of homopolar RSHs, and not of those already present in the line current of a symmetrical machine, becomes the key solution to monitor ITFs through RSHs. Finally, it must be noted that any real new IM has inherent asymmetry, which leads to the existence of these RSHs (the homopolar ones in a symmetrical IM) even when there is no ITF, but still with a much lower amplitude than the rest, also enabling a very sensitive detection when the ITF appears, as proven in Section V.

Next, a theoretical analysis is conducted to determine which are the homopolar RSHs. The research presented is limited to IMs with three phases but with any type of connection (Δ or Y). First, in Subsection II-A, the general formulation of RSHs frequencies is deduced, leading to (7) and (9), which specially reflect the initial phase of these harmonics (in the case of ν multiple and non-multiple of three, respectively), as a function of the motor parameters. Then, from these two equations, the homopolar RSHs are inferred for any IM (for every possible kR/p), leading to Table II in Subsection II-B.

A. General formulation of RSHs

Let us consider a symmetrical squirrel-cage IM ($m_s = 3$) in steady-state with a three-phase current system in the stator windings (phase currents). Now, let us assume that this system is composed of several three-phase subsystems, each with a different angular frequency $\omega_\nu = 2\pi\nu f_0$. Each of the subsystems will give rise to a series of harmonic Spatial Flux Waves (SFWs) with different number of pole pairs $h_s p$ (where h_s is an odd number that represents the relative order of the spatial harmonic).

Let us now consider first the case where ν is a non-multiple of three odd number. The fundamental harmonic SFW ($h_s = 1$) in each of the subsystems of currents can be represented in the stator reference system (s, sys) by means of a Space Phasor [36]:

$$\vec{\Phi}_{h_s=1}^{s,sys} = \left| \vec{\Phi}_{h_s=1}^{s,sys} \right| e^{j(g\omega_\nu)t} \quad (2)$$

Where $g = 1$ for positive sequence subsystems ($\nu = 6n - 5$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$) and $g = -1$ for negative sequence subsystems ($\nu = 6n - 1$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$), since different sequences generate different directions of rotation.

Each of these SFWs induce in each rotor bar ($y = 1, 2, \dots, R$) a new set of currents:

$$i_{y,r}^{h_s=1} = I_r \cos \left((g\omega_\nu - p\Omega_r)t - p(y-1)\frac{2\pi}{R} \right) \quad (3)$$

Where Ω_r is the rotor mechanical speed.

In turn, these rotor current system generates new harmonic SFWs of relative order [34]:

$$h_r = k\frac{R}{p} \pm h_s \quad (4)$$

Which in the stator reference system (s,sys) can be expressed as:

$$\vec{\Phi}_{h_r}^{s,sys} = \left| \vec{\Phi}_{h_r}^{s,sys} \right| e^{j(\pm(g\omega_\nu - p\Omega_r) + h_r p\Omega_r)t} \quad (5)$$

These space harmonics only interact with the stator if they have a relative order that the stator winding is also capable of producing. Since the stator can only produce SFWs of odd relative order h_s , the relative order of the SFW generated by the rotor h_r must be odd too to interact with the stator. Thus, a RSH exists in the stator if the relative order of its associated SFW (h_r) is odd. Since h_s is always odd, for $h_r = kR/p \pm h_s$ to be odd too, kR/p must be even. Concluding, a machine with a certain R/p only produces RSHs associated with a k that makes kR/p an even number.

Assuming that kR/p is even, these new SFWs will induce in each stator phase ($x = 1, 2, \dots, m_s$) a new set of currents:

$$i_{x,s}^{h_r} = I_s \cos \left(\pm(g\omega_\nu - p\Omega_r)t + h_r p\Omega_r t - ph_r(x-1)\frac{2\pi}{m_s p} \right) \quad (6)$$

Substituing (4) in (6), taking into account that $\Omega_{rot} = 2\pi f_0(1-s)/p$ and simplifying leads to:

$$i_{x,s}^{h_r} = I_s \cos \left(2\pi t \left[k\frac{R}{p}(1-s) \pm g\nu \right] f_0 - \left[k\frac{R}{p} \pm 1 \right] (x-1)\frac{2\pi}{m_s} \right) \quad (7)$$

Up to now, ν has been an odd number non-multiple of three. Now, let us consider the existence of subsystems of currents with homopolar sequence, as it could be the case of a delta-connected motor, i.e. ν odd multiple of three: $\nu = 6n - 3$. These subsystems are not able to generate harmonic SFWs associated to $h_s = 6n - 5$ or $h_s = 6n - 1$, only to $h_s = 6n - 3$. These harmonic SFWs are of pulsating type, that is, they have a time-varying amplitude at a fixed position in space (as opposed to a rotating wave, which has a constant amplitude at a position that varies in time). Therefore, they can be expressed, according to Leblanc's theorem, as the superposition of two space phasors of equal amplitude but different direction of rotation:

$$\vec{\Phi}_{h_s=6n-3}^{s,sys} = \frac{\left| \vec{\Phi}_{h_s=6n-3}^{s,sys} \right|}{2} e^{j(\omega_\nu)t} + \frac{\left| \vec{\Phi}_{h_s=6n-3}^{s,sys} \right|}{2} e^{j(-\omega_\nu)t} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{kR}{p} = 6m - 3 \mp 1 & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{upper signs in (7)} \rightarrow \left\{ \frac{kR}{p} = 6m - 4, (+) \cdot (g) \cdot (\nu) \right. \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{if } \nu = 6n - 5 \rightarrow g = 1 \rightarrow \nu_{sign} = (+) \cdot (+) \cdot (6n - 5) = 6n - 5 \\ \text{if } \nu = 6n - 1 \rightarrow g = -1 \rightarrow \nu_{sign} = (+) \cdot (-) \cdot (6n - 1) = -6n + 1 \end{array} \right. \\ \text{lower signs in (7)} \rightarrow \left\{ \frac{kR}{p} = 6m - 2, (-) \cdot (g) \cdot (\nu) \right. \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{if } \nu = 6n - 5 \rightarrow g = 1 \rightarrow \nu_{sign} = (-) \cdot (+) \cdot (6n - 5) = -6n + 5 \\ \text{if } \nu = 6n - 1 \rightarrow g = -1 \rightarrow \nu_{sign} = (-) \cdot (-) \cdot (6n - 1) = 6n - 1 \end{array} \right. \end{array} \right. \\
 \frac{kR}{p} = 6m - 3 \mp 3 & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{upper signs in (9)} \rightarrow \left\{ \frac{kR}{p} = 6m - 6, (+) \cdot (\nu) \right. \left\{ \text{if } \nu = 6n - 3 \rightarrow \nu_{sign} = (+) \cdot (6n - 3) = 6n - 3 \right. \\ \text{lower signs in (9)} \rightarrow \left\{ \frac{kR}{p} = 6m, (-) \cdot (\nu) \right. \left\{ \text{if } \nu = 6n - 3 \rightarrow \nu_{sign} = (-) \cdot (6n - 3) = -6n + 3 \right. \end{array} \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

 Fig. 1. Deducing the ν_{sign} of the homopolar RSHs for each set of kR/p .

Applying the same procedure as before, but taking now into account that $h_s = 3$ is the minimum h_s for which these subsystems produce a magnetic field (previously was $h_s = 1$):

$$\begin{aligned}
 i_{x,s}^{h_r} = I_s \cos \left(2\pi t \left[k \frac{R}{p} (1-s) \pm \nu \right] f_0 \right. \\
 \left. - \left[k \frac{R}{p} \pm 3 \right] (x-1) \frac{2\pi}{m_s} \right) \quad (9)
 \end{aligned}$$

B. Deducing the homopolar RSHs

Previous equations show the *main* mechanism of RSH production in the phase currents of a squirrel-cage IM (main: interaction through the lowest h_s). From them, the following rules can be drawn for the existence of a RSH associated with a given k and ν , as defined in (1), in the stator line current of a symmetrical machine:

- 1) A time harmonic $f_\nu = \nu f_0$ must exist in the stator.
- 2) k must be an integer such that kR/p is an even number.
- 3) Systems given by (7) and (9) must not be homopolar.

As for the first rule, there are always time harmonics of up to at least $\nu = 5$, coming either from the grid or generated in the machine due to the non-linear characteristic of the iron. Regarding the second rule, there is always a k such that kR/p is even, since R and p are integers. As for the third rule, the system is homopolar if the factor multiplying $(x-1)2\pi/m_s$, which is $(kR/p \pm 1)$ in (7) and $(kR/p \pm 3)$ in (9), is a multiple of three. Let us now analyze when RSHs form a homopolar system to deduce which of them are absent in the symmetrical IM, but appear when stator symmetry is lost under an ITF.

From (7), it follows that $kR/p \pm 1 = 3n$ (with $n \in \mathbb{N}$) for it to form a homopolar system. Therefore, $kR/p = 3n \mp 1$. At the same time, kR/p must be an even number. Then, $3n$ must be odd, which implies that n must be odd too: $n = 2m - 1$ (with $m \in \mathbb{N}$). Therefore, $kR/p = 6m - 3 \mp 1$ for system (7) to be homopolar. Applying an analogous reasoning, it follows from (9) that $kR/p = 6m - 3 \mp 3$ for this system to be homopolar.

Last steps are reflected in Fig. 1, starting on its left with: $kR/p = 6m - 3 \mp 1$ and $kR/p = 6m - 3 \mp 3$. These last two equations have an upper and lower sign, which correspond to those in front of ν in (7) and (9). Thus, by considering in Fig.

TABLE II
 ν_{sign} OF THE HOMOPOLAR RSHs FOR EACH SET OF kR/p

$kR/p \in 6m - 4$	$kR/p \in 6m - 2$	$kR/p \in 6m$
$\pm 6(n-1) + 1$	$\pm 6(n-1) - 1$	$\pm(6n-3)$

1 each of these signs separately, it is possible to determine, for each set of kR/p , the values of ν for which their related RSHs are homopolar. The deduction process shown in Fig. 1 leads to the determination of ν_{sign} , which is the result of combining ν and the resulting sign in front of it. Then, these sets can be classified in three groups of kR/p that cover all possible cases, as shown in Table II.

It must be remarked that the amplitude of RSHs decreases the higher the value of $|\nu_{sign}|$ and k . Thus, among the homopolar RSHs(ν_{sign}) sets given by Table II, those of lower $|\nu_{sign}|$ and lower k (that makes kR/p an even number) will be used. Finally, it should also be noted that, since it is always possible to select a value for k that makes kR/p an even number (no matter what is the number of bars and pole pairs), it is always possible to choose a homopolar-RSH as an ITF indicator in any induction machine, thus being a general approach for three-phase induction machines.

III. DIAGNOSIS APPROACH

In this section, an ITF detection method is proposed based on continuously monitoring the amplitudes of the RSHs that form a homopolar system in a symmetrical machine. This approach (depicted in Fig. 2) consists of three different blocks: slip estimation algorithm (Block A, [37]), selection of homopolar RSHs (Block B) and diagnosis (Block C).

A. Block A: Slip estimation algorithm

In order to use slip-dependent harmonics for diagnosis purposes, as it is proposed in this paper with the homopolar RSHs, the slip estimation is a critical step without which one cannot reliably locate them in the current spectrum [38], [39]: a precise slip estimation allows a precise harmonic location and a reliable amplitude extraction. This is even more critical

Fig. 2. Flux diagram of the proposed diagnosis scheme.

in the proposed approach as a specific set of RSHs is proposed as ITF indicators, among of all those present in the spectrum. Therefore, the objective of this section is to introduce the slip-estimation algorithm that the proposed approach must incorporate to provide a reliable detection.

To address this issue, the algorithm described in [37] is used: tested successfully in 100 industrial motors, it estimates slip in a precise and automatic way, only through a current measurement in normal operation. This algorithm applies an iterative procedure that completely localizes and characterizes the RSHs from scratch, determining their frequencies, ν_{sign} and kR/p (without the need to know R). Then, using these three parameters, it calculates the slip. Thus, this algorithm delivers both the value of kR/p that is necessary to select the homopolar RSHs from Table II and the slip needed to locate them in the spectrum.

It should be noted that homopolar RSHs may not be found among the RSHs characterized by the algorithm, since they have a low amplitude at healthy state and the algorithm of [37] is based on detecting the maximum in a given window. However, as the algorithm provides both kR/p and the slip, the ν_{sign} of the homopolar RSHs can be obtained through Table II using kR/p , while their frequencies can be calculated through equation (1) using kR/p , ν_{sign} and slip, thereby enabling their accurate localization in the spectrum and their amplitude quantification (zero or very low under healthy state, or significant under ITF).

Moreover, the estimated slip can be used as an auxiliary indicator to discriminate when a RSH amplitude variation is due to a load change, and when it is due to an ITF (as explained in Subsection III-C).

B. Block B: Selection of homopolar RSHs

kR/p (obtained in the previous step using [37]) is used to select from Table II the values of ν_{sign} linked to the homopolar RSHs, used to monitor the ITF. Finally, kR/p , the slip and ν_{sign} are input to Block C to locate and quantify the homopolar RSHs.

C. Block C: Diagnosis

Appearance of ITFs highly increase the amplitude of the selected RSHs. Nevertheless, load changes, the appearance of eccentricity and voltage unbalances can also affect these RSHs (other faults that produce components at different frequencies than those of RSHs (e.g., rotor electrical asymmetries [24])

TABLE III
CORRELATION BETWEEN AUXILIARY INDICATORS AND PHENOMENA AFFECTING THE AMPLITUDE OF RSHs.

	ITF	Load Changes	Eccentricity	Voltage Unbalance
CUI	✓	✓	✗	✓
VUI	✗	✗	✗	✓
Slip	✗	✓	✗	✗

or ambient temperature variations do not affect these RSHs). Yet, it is possible to distinguish between ITFs and these other phenomena by also monitoring the slip, and the Voltage and Current Unbalance Indexes (VUI and CUI) (defined as per MG-1-2016). Table III shows if these auxiliary indicators (CUI, VUI and slip) are affected or not by phenomena that can change RSHs amplitude. According to it, a RSH amplitude variation due to a load change can be discriminated by checking if the slip has changed: ITF hardly changes the slip, while the load change does. Then, a variation due to an increase in eccentricity can be differentiated by checking whether the CUI has changed: ITF highly modifies CUI, while eccentricity hardly does. The variation due to voltage unbalance can be differentiated by checking whether the VUI has changed: ITF hardly modifies the VUI, while voltage unbalance does. Moreover, it should be noted that any effect that the saturation level may have on the amplitude of the RSHs, either because it varies due to a modification of the load level or the supply voltage, can also be discriminated with slip monitoring, since both the modification of the load level and the supply voltages cause important changes in this auxiliary indicator. Furthermore, the diagnosis scheme shown in Fig. 2 does not distinguish a scenario where VU and ITF increase in the same measurement, from one in which only the VU increases, since both might lead to similar effects in the indicators. However, an ITF starts with a high contact resistance and, consequently, a low short-circuit current. Thus, the ITF develops slowly during this initial phase, enabling ITF detection in the next measurement, where the chances to have a second VU are very low. First, because, as demonstrated in the paper, ITFs do not increase VU, and second, because for a VU to worsen or create an ITF, it must be very high and persist for sufficient time. Yet, this abnormal condition would be detected by the system or protections and the motor would be stopped to properly correct the VU before an ITF is created. The same applies in case of a simultaneous increase of the load and ITF severity. Thus, based on these correlation principles

TABLE IV
SIMULATED MOTOR CHARACTERISTICS

	P_N (kW)	V_N (V)	Pole pairs	Bars	Min. ITF (%)
M1 (Δ)	4	230	2	28	0.34
M2 (Δ)	22	400	1	30	1.52
M3 (Y)	1120	6600	3	70	0.93

(summarized in Table III, and proven in further sections), a robust diagnosis algorithm is build (Fig. 2).

Finally, it must be remembered that the proposed methodology is conceived as a continuous monitoring fault detection system, where measurements and indicators are taken and calculated continuously. In this regard, it must be pointed out that, in a real industrial environment there are not constant magnitudes (as simplified in Table III): two consecutive measurements will lead to different values of the indicator evaluated, even if the conditions are practically identical. Hence, thresholds to determine when a change in the indicators has occurred must be established during the initial period of measurements by determining what are the usual variations that the indicators undergo during the normal operation of the motor at healthy state (i.e. arbitrary variations due to small changes in the measurement conditions). Additionally, Table III simplifies as a constant indicator scenario (slip, VUI and CUI not varying), what in real life is a "moderate" change. A statistical analysis of the results presented in the following sections leads to the following thresholds: if the slip variation is higher than 0.2 pp, it is considered a load variation and not an ITF; if the VUI variation is higher than 0.09 pp, it is considered a voltage unbalance and not an ITF; if the CUI variation is lower than 0.1 pp, it is considered an eccentricity fault and not an ITF; if the RSH amplitude variation is lower than 0.6 dB, it is due to small changes in the measurement conditions and/or measurement errors and not an ITF. Summarizing all the thresholds introduced: if the RSH amplitude variation is greater than 0.6 dB, the slip variation is below 0.2 pp, the VUI variation is below 0.09 pp and the CUI variation is higher than 0.1 pp, an alarm is set for the ITF. The thresholds here established should be understood as a first paradigm which must be further analyzed with more extensive results.

IV. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS VERIFICATION

To confirm the theoretical analysis and subsequent fault detection approach conducted in Sections II and III, the models of three IMs (M1, M2 and M3) of very different characteristics and with different winding connections (see Table IV and Fig. 3) have been built with Ansys Maxwell FEA software using their real geometries, winding configuration and B-H characteristics. The three groups of Table II are covered through the three simulated motors. Each motor has been modeled as a healthy machine and as a machine with an ITF (created as in [40]) of minimum fault severity (one shorted turn). Last column of Table IV shows the percentage of shorted turns (ST) that represents the minimum ITF in each motor, this being the definition of the fault level. Each simulation is run with a time step of $80 \mu s$ at full and no load, with a 50

Fig. 3. Cross-section of simulated motors: (a) M1, (b) M2, and (c) M3.

Hz perfectly sinusoidal line voltage supply. Additionally, extra simulations are run at full load, with eccentricity and voltage unbalance, both cases under healthy state and with ITF.

A. Healthy and ITF at different loads

As shown in Table IV, M1 has $R/p = 28/2 = 14$, therefore, the minimum k that makes kR/p an even number is 1. Since $kR/p = 14 \in 6m - 4$, according to Table II, the main homopolar RSHs are RSHs(-5, 1) (main: minimum $|\nu_{sign}|$). With an analogous reasoning, these harmonics are RSHs(-3, 3) with $k = 1$ for M2, and RSHs(-1, 5) with $k = 3$ for M3. Figures 4, 5 and 6 show the line current spectrums at full load (left subfigs.) and no load (right subfigs.). The six RSHs marked with circles are (from left to right): RSHs($\nu_{sign} = [-5, -3, \dots, 5]$) with $k = 1$ for M1 and M2, and with $k = 3$ for M3. In healthy state (upper subfigs.), apart from the odd multiples of f_0 , only the RSHs that do not form a homopolar system (marked in black) are clearly present (have a high amplitude), while the homopolar RSHs determined by Table II (marked in red) are absent (at their position, the amplitude is that of the noise-floor). In faulty state (lower subfigs., min. ITF), homopolar RSHs predicted by Table II undergo a very high increase in amplitude (35, 40, 50 and even 65 dB). However, the amplitude of the rest of RSHs remain virtually unchanged

Fig. 4. Line current spectrum of Motor 1: (a) full load, (b) no load.

Fig. 5. Line current spectrum of Motor 2: (a) full load, (b) no load.

Fig. 6. Line current spectrum of Motor 3: (a) full load, (b) no load.

in comparison. From 24 cases (3 x 4 non-homopolar RSH per motor x 2 load levels), 20 experience changes of 1 dB or less, 3 of them have changes of around 1.5 dB, and only 1 changes 2.5 dB. Therefore, simulation results match theory for every case, confirming that homopolar RSHs predicted by Table II are excellent indicators of the ITF presence, even at its minimum severity, while the rest are useless.

Table V shows, for the two homopolar RSHs (RSH₁; negative ν_{sign} , RSH₂; positive), to be used as ITF indicators, and each motor analyzed: ν_{sign} , frequency, and healthy (H) and faulty (F) amplitude, at full load (FL) and No Load (NL) (slip is virtually the same for healthy and faulty state and so are the frequencies). For the entire load range and for all motors under ITF, at least one of the two homopolar RSHs has an amplitude that clearly stands out from the noise level. In the worst case (M3 at full load, with especially low RSHs since they are related to $k = 3$), the highest amplitude homopolar RSH is at -85 dB: at least 10 dB above the usual noise level that could be achieved under industrial conditions (around [-95 -105] dB) with adequate signal acquisition and conditioning (≥ 12 bits ADC, full use of ADC input range, antialiasing filters, etc.). Finally, load variations affect each motor differently. In M1 and M3, RSHs₁ highly decrease its amplitude with increasing load, while the RSHs₂ are much less affected. Conversely, in M2, both homopolar RSHs highly increase with increasing load. In any case, since the ITF has a negligible effect on the slip (unlike the load change), it is possible to discern when a variation in the homopolar RSH amplitude is due to a change in load and when to an ITF.

Concluding, the results confirm that the homopolar RSHs are excellent ITF indicators, even at its minimum severity, being the only ones that show sensitivity to the fault, even at both ends of the operating range.

B. Extra asymmetry: eccentricity

Each motor has been simulated under a mixed eccentricity (ME) level of 40% (20% static + 20% dynamic), which is between an unacceptable value and a problem requiring immediate motor decommission [41]. Figure 7 shows the amplitude of the homopolar RSHs used as ITF indicators (upper subfigs.) and the CUI (lower subfigs.) in each of the conditions (healthy, ITF, ME and ME+ITF). As can be seen, both ME and ITF separately increase the homopolar RSHs amplitudes, but it is possible to differentiate between them: ITF highly varies the CUI (0.35 to 1 pp), while ME hardly does (0.01 to 0.09 pp). Finally, the ITF can be detected even with a preexistent ME, since at least one of the homopolar RSHs highly increases (32 dB in M1, 7 dB in M2 and 34 dB in M3).

C. Extra asymmetry: voltage unbalance

Each motor has been simulated under a voltage unbalance (VU) level of 1% (according to NEMA MG 1-2016, above this VU level the motor power should be derated to reduce potential damage). Figure 8 shows the amplitude of the homopolar RSHs used as ITF indicators (upper subfigs.) and the CUI (lower subfigs.) in each of the conditions (healthy, ITF, VU, VU + MIN ITF, VU + second ITF level). As can be seen, both VU and ITF separately increase the homopolar RSHs amplitudes. On the other hand, CUI cannot be used to differentiate these faults, since it increases under both ITF (from 0.35 to 1.1%) and VU (from 6 to 11%). It is necessary to use the VUI, which precisely measures the VU (in this case is 1%), but it is barely modified under an ITF. Finally,

TABLE V

 ν_{sign} , FREQUENCY AND HEALTHY AND FAULTY AMPLITUDE OF THE HOMOPOLAR RSHs (USED AS ITF INDICATORS) AT FULL AND NO LOAD.

	RSH ₁						RSH ₂							
	ν_{sign}	f_{FL} (Hz)	$A_{FL,H}$ (dB)	$A_{FL,F}$ (dB)	f_{NL} (Hz)	$A_{NL,H}$ (dB)	$A_{NL,F}$ (dB)	ν_{sign}	f_{FL} (Hz)	$A_{FL,H}$ (dB)	$A_{FL,F}$ (dB)	f_{NL} (Hz)	$A_{NL,H}$ (dB)	$A_{NL,F}$ (dB)
M1	-5	435	-121	-84	449	-112	-75	1	735	-118	-52	749	-118	-48
M2	-3	1300	-121	-67	1348	-120	-86	3	1600	-113	-69	1648	-116	-85
M3	-1	3437	-126	-85	3449	-126	-66	5	3737	-130	-93	3749	-133	-94

Fig. 7. Amplitude of homopolar RSHs used as ITF indicators (a) and CUI (b).

Fig. 8. Amplitude of homopolar RSHs used as ITF indicators (a) and CUI (b).

the ITF can be detected even with a preexistent VU, since at least one of the homopolar RSH increases its amplitude when the minimum ITF is created. This increase is between 1 to 2.3 dB. When the second ITF level is introduced (2 ST), the homopolar RSHs experience a very significant increase in M1 (5.6 dB) and in M2 (5 dB). In M3, it is necessary to also monitor the next upper homopolar RSH provided by Table I (RSH(11)) to achieve high sensitivity (about 4.5 dB). In this way, it is proved the efficacy of the methodology at a still early stage ITF, even with preexistent VU.

V. LABORATORY TEST

The research presented shows how the homopolar RSHs from Table II are very sensitive to the ITF, and hence can be used as very reliable indicators to detect it, even at its earliest state. In this section, the proposed approach is validated using a real IM.

A. Setup

The setup used to conduct the tests is shown in Fig. 9. For a better understanding, it has been represented as an scheme in Fig. 10. It consists of a Magtrol AHB-24 controlled hysteresis brake (24 Nm rated torque; label 1) coupled to a RAEL RL90L-4 IM (1.5 kW, 400 V, 3.8 A, 1400 rpm, 4-poles, 46 bars, 294 Tph, Y-connected; label 2), directly fed from the grid. The IM has a modified stator winding with three additional taps, R_1 , R_2 , R_3 , (label 3) in winding $R - R'$ as shown in Fig. 11, which only allows to short-circuit three different percentages of turns through a switch (label 4): 0% ($A - A_0$), 3.4% ($A - A_1$), 6.8% ($A - A_2$) and 10.2% ($A - A_3$). To emulate a more incipient fault and protect the winding integrity, a variable contact resistance, R_c (label 5), is inserted in series with the shorted loop. As for the DAQ, a NI USB-6212 (16 bits ADC resolution; label 6) is used to capture the three line currents, through Pico TA189 clamps ($\pm 1\%$ of reading ± 2 mA accuracy; label 7), and the three line voltages, through RS-SI 7002 voltage probes (label 8), from which the slip, homopolar RSHs amplitude, CUI and VUI are obtained. The load torque is modified through a DC source (label 9). This setup also allows the supply to be provided either from the grid (with the possibility to create a voltage unbalance through a variable resistance) or from a VFD. Finally, in order to increase artificially the level of ME, a similar approach to the one used in [42] has been followed, which consists of placing a washer under one of the motors support, thereby creating additional static, dynamic and conical eccentricity (radial and axial eccentricity of the air gap) [42], [43].

The method must be able to detect a low severity fault, that is, a fault that leads to a low short-circuit current. The magnitude of the short-circuit current depends on R_c and the percentage of STs. In the lab motor, the first possible % of STs is 3.4%. This fault stage leads to a high short-circuit current when a typical value for the contact resistance at advanced fault stages is used: $R_c \in [0.1, 1] \Omega$. To reduce this current, and prove the method detects the fault even under the hardest conditions (low severity fault), contact resistance R_c is increased to 2.52 Ω , reducing the short-circuit current to a very low value: 28.16% of rated current. Moreover, as

Fig. 9. Experimental setup.

Fig. 10. Scheme of the experimental setup.

 Fig. 11. Scheme of phase winding $R - R'$ with the additional taps.

seen in Section V-C5, when R_c is reduced from 2.52 to 0.88 Ω , the short-circuit current increases from 28 to 100%, and the homopolar RSHs experience a much higher increase in amplitude under the ITF appearance, proving that increasing R_c helps to test the method in very challenging conditions (very low severity fault).

B. Methodology of analysis

As this motor has $R/p = 46/2 = 23$, the minimum k that makes kR/p an even number is 2. According to Table II, $kR/p = 2 \cdot 46/2 = 46$ belongs to the set $6m - 2$, thus, in healthy state, homopolar RSHs(-1, 5) should show lower amplitudes than RSHs(-5, -3, 1, 3), thereby being more sensitive to the fault. To verify this, the amplitude of the RSHs is computed according to the following methodology:

For all experiments, the line current is recorded at a sampling rate of 40 kS/s with a time duration of 50 s. Then, it is divided in time sequences of 5 s ([0 5], [5 10], [15 20], etc.). For each of these time sequences, the FFT is applied and the amplitude of RSHs(-5, -3, -1, 1, 3, 5) is recorded in dB with respect to the fundamental component. Finally, the average amplitude of each RSH is obtained. The same procedure is followed for the slip, CUI and VUI calculation.

TABLE VI
SHORT CIRCUIT CURRENTS FOR EACH CONDITION.

		LOAD LEVEL			
		100%	75%	50%	30%
ST	3.4%	28.16%	30.75%	40.56%	52.78%
	6.8%	50.26%	72.18%	88.67%	103.00%
	10.2%	98.42%	-	-	-

This method allows mitigating small and random perturbations in test conditions during the recording of the signals, as well as errors introduced by the DAQ.

It should be noted that for these experiments, a sampling frequency of 40 kHz was used as they were performed in the context of a wider project where this sampling frequency was required to analyze other signals. However, since in the proposed approach the frequencies of the homopolar RSHs are known (thanks to the slip estimation algorithm), this sampling frequency could be adjusted (if needed by technical limitations) to cover only up to the upper limit of the bandwidth of the homopolar RSH of higher frequency. In any case, most commercial DAQs can achieve 40 kHz while taking a 50 s signal.

C. Experimental results

Using the setup described, line R current has been acquired for each fault state at 100, 75, 50 and 30% of load both with Grid-supply and with VFD-supply at 50 Hz. At loads lower than 100%, only the first two fault states are reached, since the short-circuit current exceeds the rated value at the third fault state. No tests have been performed below 30% of load since the short-circuit current exceeds the rated value at the third and second fault states. Table VI shows the short circuit current (in % of the rated current), for each tested condition: it increases with the number of shorted turns, and decreases with the load.

Moreover, additional tests have been performed at full load considering different levels of VU and ME for each fault state. Finally, an additional test has been performed at full load and 3.4% of ST with grid supply and no extra asymmetry, using a contact resistance of 0.88 Ω to prove the efficacy of the method also under a realistic value of $R_c \in [0.1 \ 1] \Omega$ at advance fault stages.

Before proceeding with the results, it is important to remark that the motor used in this setup has skewed bars, which reduces RSHs amplitude [37]. Moreover, the homopolar RSHs used as fault indicators belong to $k = 2$, since R/p is odd, which is also a factor that reduces their amplitude. Therefore, if the methodology works under one of the most challenging cases, it will also work in those motors where the homopolar RSHs to use are those belonging to $k = 1$ (motors with R/p even). In this regard and according to the database in [44], which contains information on 3643 IMs, most two-poles (98.8%) and most four-poles (72%) three-phase induction motors (the two most common type of induction motors in used) are built with an even number of R/p . Finally, it must also be remarked that the challenging scenario of VFD-supply has been considered. In this scenario, the main challenge is

TABLE VII
AMPLITUDE FOR EACH LOAD LEVEL (ROWS) AND (%) OF STs (COLUMNS)
OF THE HOMOPOLAR RSHs: RSH(-1) (BLUE), RSH(+5) (RED).

	0%	3.4%	6.8%	10.2%
30%	-94.8 -93.4	-91.7 -90.8	-80.8 -85.1	-
50%	-96.4 -93.4	-92.5 -90.0	-83.6 -85.2	-
75%	-99.2 -91.8	-96.5 -90.8	-86.6 -85.7	-
100%	-101.4 -92.70	-98.7 -91.5	-88.5 -86.0	-86.9 -82.9

the amplitude extraction of the harmonic, due to the higher harmonic content of the spectrum and the potential higher noise. However, thanks to the speed estimation algorithm used [37], which has been tested satisfactorily in more than 20 VFD-fed industrial motors, and a proper signal acquisition and conditioning (≥ 12 bits ADC, full use of ADC input range, antialiasing filters, etc.), the amplitude of the homopolar RSHs could be extracted as in the case of grid supply.

1) *Tests at different loads with $R_c = 2.52 \Omega$* : Figure 12 shows the amplitudes of several RSHs for each fault state and load condition. Figure 13 shows the results in Fig. 12 restricted to the homopolar RSHs, while Figs. 14 and 15 show the line current spectra around these homopolar RSHs in one of the windows under analysis. The harmonics predicted by Table II, RSHs(-1, 5) (highlighted with continuous trace in Fig. 12), are indeed the ones with the lowest amplitude in healthy state. Then, as the fault severity is increased, these are the only harmonics that continuously increase at all load levels, showing variations of up to 10.9 dB for RSH(-1), and 5.8 dB for RSH(5), when going from 3.4% to 6.8% of ST (see Fig. 13). Furthermore, it is observed that the amplitude of RSH(-1) progressively decreases with the load level (see Fig. 16a and blue colored values in Table VII), while RSH(5) remains practically unchanged (see Fig. 16b and red colored values in Table VII); simulated motor M3, which belongs to the same group ($kR/p \in 6m - 2$), behaves the same way. In any case, as the slip is monitored along with the homopolar RSHs amplitude, it is possible to determine when the variation comes from a load change or an ITF. In this regard, Fig. 17 shows the VUI, CUI and slip for each fault state and load condition. As can be seen, the VUI and slip practically remain constant across the different ITF levels, while the CUI shows great variations, just as stated in Section III. Finally, it is worth to remark that the method works even with a very small current of 28.16% (see Table VI), achieved at the lowest fault severity and the highest load.

2) *Tests at different ME levels with $R_c = 2.52 \Omega$* : Figure 18 and Table VIII show the amplitudes of the homopolar RSHs at full load for each fault state, considering two different ME levels: inherent, and artificially crated ME (note that the latter results in an increase of the ME harmonics of 6 dB with respect to the inherent ME). First, it is important to remark that the asymmetry introduced by the ME affects differently both harmonics, as they are associated to SFW of different direction of rotation, therefore it is necessary to always monitor both of them. In this regard, it is observed that at least one of the homopolar RSHs (in this case RSH(5)) maintains a continuous increasing behavior with good sensitivity regardless of the

Fig. 12. RSHs amplitude for each fault state: (a) 100%, (b) 75%, (c) 50% and (d) 30% of load.

Fig. 13. Amplitude variation with respect to the previous fault state for each load condition of the homopolar RSHs: (a) RSH(-1), (b) RSH(+5).

ME considered. Therefore, the methodology is effective under pre-existent high levels of ME, thereby confirming simulation results. Finally, in order to determine when a variation of the RSHs amplitude comes from a ME level change and when from an increase in the ITF severity, the CUI must be used. As seen in Fig. 19, a change in the ITF severity modifies the CUI, while a change in the ME level does not.

Fig. 14. RSH(-1) in the spectrum of the line current for different % of ST and loads: (a) 100%, (b) 75%, (c) 50% and (d) 30% of load.

Fig. 15. RSH(5) in the spectrum of the line current for different % of ST and loads: (a) 100%, (b) 75%, (c) 50% and (d) 30% of load.

3) *Tests at different VU levels with $R_c = 2.52 \Omega$* : Figure 20 and Table IX show the amplitudes of the homopolar RSHs at full load for each fault state, considering three different VU levels: 0.63% (inherent), 1% and 1.5% (note that the latter would be considered as an unacceptable value to operate an IM according to NEMA MG 1-2016). As with the ME case, the asymmetry introduced by the VU affects both harmonics differently. Yet, it is observed that at least one of the homopolar RSHs (RSH(5)) maintains a continuous increasing behavior with good sensitivity regardless of the VU considered. Therefore, the methodology is effective under pre-existent high levels of VU, thereby confirming simulation results. Finally, in order to determine when a variation of the RSHs amplitude comes from a VU level change and when from an increase in the ITF severity, the VUI must be used. As seen in Fig. 21, a change in VU level modifies the VUI, while a change in the ITF severity does not.

Fig. 16. Amplitude for each load level and (%) of STs of the homopolar RSHs: (a) RSH(-1), (b) RSH(+5).

Fig. 17. Auxiliary indicators at different loads and (%) of STs.

4) *Tests at different loads with $R_c = 2.52 \Omega$ and VFD-supply*: Figures 22a and 22b show the spectrums for the cases of Grid- and VFD-supply (50 Hz), both at the same load level, while Figs. 22c and 22d show a zoom around the RSHs (homopolar ones are marked with red circles). As can be seen, the amplitudes of the homopolar RSHs are also extracted with accuracy in the case of the VFD-supply. This is achieved thanks to the speed estimation algorithm (the challenge of a more populated spectrum is overcome) and a proper signal acquisition plus conditioning (a noise-floor similar to the case of Grid-supply is reached, allowing detection of low amplitude harmonics). From Figs. 22c and 22d it is also clear that homopolar RSHs, either in the case of Grid-supply or VFD-supply, are the ones that experience the highest increase when the ITF is introduced (12 and 4.6 dB with Grid-supply, and 10 and 7 dB with VFD-supply). The amplitude of the non-homopolar RSHs either decreases (RSHs(-5, -3, -1)) or experience a lower increase (RSH(+3) with 3.5 dB, Grid-supply, and 3.3 dB, VFD-supply). Furthermore, Fig. 23 shows the amplitudes of the RSHs (homopolar ones highlighted with continuous trace) for the same loads and fault states as in Fig. 12 of Subsection V-C1, but with VFD-supply. As can be seen, also with VFD-supply, the homopolar RSHs are the ones with lowest amplitude in healthy state, and the only ones that, for all load levels, increase continuously as the fault severity increases, thus reaching the same conclusion as with simulation results and Grid-supply results. Finally, Fig. 24 and

Fig. 18. Amplitude for each ME level and (%) of STs of the homopolar RSHs: (a) RSH(-1), (b) RSH(+5).

Fig. 19. Auxiliary indicators at different ME levels and (%) of STs.

Table X show the amplitudes of the homopolar RSHs for these load levels and fault states. As can be seen, both harmonics show a good correlation with the fault severity. Therefore, the methodology can also be used under VFD-supply. As in the case of Grid-supply, in order to determine when a variation of the RSHs amplitude comes from a load change and when from an increase in the ITF severity, the slip must be used. As seen in Fig. 25, a change in the load modifies the slip, while a change in the ITF severity does not.

5) *Test with $R_c \in [0.1 \ 1] \ \Omega$* : Table XI shows the results of the experiment conducted using $R_c = 0.88 \ \Omega$ at full load: amplitude with 0% and 3.4% of ST. As can be seen, the harmonics of lowest amplitude in healthy state are the homopolar RSHs, RSH(-1) (blue) and RSH(5) (red), just as expected according to Section II. When the fault is introduced, the most sensitive harmonic is RSH(-1) with a variation of 13.9 dB, followed by RSH(3) and RSH(5), with a variation of 6.8 and 5.3 dB. Then, it is again confirmed that the harmonics predicted as absent in Table II are the most sensitive to the fault. Finally, it is worth to remark that the amplitude variation of RSHs(-1, 5) when going from 0 to 3.4% of ST is much higher than in the case where $R_c = 2.52 \ \Omega$ (see Fig. 13 in Subsection V-C1). Therefore, this confirms that the experiments in previous sections with $R_c = 2.52 \ \Omega$ were the most challenging for the methodology.

TABLE VIII
AMPLITUDE FOR EACH ME LEVEL (ROWS) AND (%) OF STs (COLUMNS) OF THE HOMOPOLAR RSHs: RSH(-1) (BLUE), RSH(+5) (RED).

	0%	3.4%	6.8%	10.2%
Inherent. ME	-99.8 -93.4	-98.70 -92.3	-90.4 -88.3	-87.9 -84.6
Art. ME	-97.1 -95.5	-103.8 -94.6	-90.6 -89.3	-88.8 -85.0

Fig. 20. Amplitude for each VU level and (%) of STs of the homopolar RSHs: (a) RSH(-1), (b) RSH(+5).

Fig. 21. Auxiliary indicators at different VU levels and (%) of STs.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proves that, for every motor, homopolar RSHs are very reliable ITF indicators: they experience a radical amplitude increase even under low severity faults (as opposed to RSHs used in state of the art, which might be even completely insensitive). Homopolar RSHs are the ones that form a homopolar system in a symmetrical machine, and appear in the line current at that same frequencies under an ITF. By tracking the amplitudes of these line current harmonics, the paper proposes a general approach that solves reliably the crucial problem of ITF detection at early stages during normal operation. Additionally, this approach presents a methodology to determine which are the homopolar RSHs for each given motor. Finally, it also includes a procedure to automatically and reliably select and detect these harmonics, as well as a methodology to ensure robustness against load, eccentricity and voltage unbalance variations. The main contributions and findings are:

- Homopolar RSHs show the highest sensitivity to the ITF;

TABLE IX
AMPLITUDE FOR EACH VU LEVEL (ROWS) AND (%) OF STS (COLUMNS)
OF THE HOMOPOLAR RSHs: RSH(-1) (BLUE), RSH(+5) (RED).

	0%	3.4%	6.8%	10.2%
0.63%	-101.4 -92.70	-98.7 -91.5	-88.5 -86.0	-86.9 -82.9
1%	-89.5 -94.4	-95.8 -92.4	-90.1 -87.3	-85.9 -84.3
1.5%	-87.5 -97.0	-92.0 -93.8	-88.9 -87.3	-85.0 -84.0

Fig. 22. Spectrum comparison between Grid- and VFD-supply at same load: (a) Grid, (b) VFD, (c) grid zoomed (d) VFD zoomed.

therefore, these are the harmonics that must be used as ITF indicators.

- A theoretical analysis has been conducted, allowing to determine which are the homopolar RSHs in a symmetrical machine for each possible value of kR/p (Table II).
- The diagnosis approach incorporates a slip estimation algorithm that allows to automatically locate the RSHs, while providing kR/p , the parameter needed to select the homopolar RSHs from Table II, hence, providing a general methodology that can be applied to any motor.
- It also incorporates the monitoring of three auxiliary indicators (slip, CUI and VUI) to ensure robustness against load, eccentricity and voltage unbalance changes.
- The approach has been verified by FEA in three IMs that cover each one of the cases in Table II. The results clearly show how the homopolar RSHs dramatically increase (up

Fig. 23. RSHs amplitude for each fault state with VFD-supply: (a) 100%, (b) 75%, (c) 50% and (d) 30% of load.

TABLE X
AMPLITUDE FOR EACH LOAD LEVEL (ROWS) AND (%) OF STS (COLUMNS)
OF THE HOMOPOLAR RSHs WITH VFD-SUPPLY: RSH(-1) (BLUE),
RSH(+5) (RED).

	0%	3.4%	6.8%	10.2%
30%	-95.4 -97.3	-92.1 -93.2	-82.7 -87.5	-
50%	-95.2 -96.0	-94.3 -93.2	-85.8 -87.3	-
75%	-97.6 -96.4	-96.5 -92.9	-89.4 -87.8	-
100%	-98.1 -96.1	-97.4 -96.0	-93.5 -91.5	-89.6 -88.4

to 65 dB under ideal measurement), in both no- and full-load condition, when the minimum fault severity ITF is introduced (providing a very sensitive detection method), while the ones that were present in healthy state remain practically unchanged.

- It has also been proven that the monitoring of the slip, CUI and VUI effectively allows discrimination between

Fig. 24. Amplitude for each load level and (%) of STs of the homopolar RSHs with VFD-supply: (a) RSH(-1), (b) RSH(+5).

Fig. 25. Auxiliary indicators at different loads and (%) of STs with VFD-supply.

ITF and load, eccentricity or voltage unbalance variations.

- The approach has also been tested under preexistent high levels of eccentricity (40%) and voltage unbalance (1%), showing its efficacy to detect early-stage ITFs.
- Finally, the approach has been tested using a real IM, in a challenging scenario (the IM does not produce PSHs and has skewed bars), under different supplies, loads, VU, eccentricity, contact resistance and fault severity. In all cases, the results agree with the theoretical analysis, showing how homopolar RSHs (in this case RSHs(-1, 5) according to Table II), are the harmonics that show the best sensitivity (up to 13.9 dB) and correlation with the fault (as the fault severity increases, the indicator also increases).

Therefore, based on the results obtained, it is concluded that homopolar RSHs can be effectively used in all induction motors since: they exist and can be selected in all of them, upon fault occurrence they have a large enough amplitude to be detected with proper signal acquisition (this is proved in the paper for homopolar RSHs linked to k equal to 1, 2 and 3, which are the most common cases), and they show a high sensitivity to the ITF under different conditions of load, supply and pre-existent levels of eccentricity and voltage unbalance, and contact resistance. For those motors where RSHs have lower amplitude, that is, those built with a combination of R/p such that the minimum k that makes R/p an even number is greater than 3 (in the database of [44] only 10.7% of the IMs

TABLE XI
RSHs AT FULL LOAD AND $R_c = 0.88 \Omega$: AMPLITUDE WITH 0% AND 3.4% OF SHORTED TURNS AND VARIATION (ΔA) BETWEEN STATES.

	0% ST	3.4% ST	ΔA
RSH(-5)	-88.1	-91.4	-3.3
RSH(-3)	-74.8	-76.1	-1.3
RSH(-1)	-103.1	-89.2	13.9
RSH(+1)	-78.0	-80.8	-2.9
RSH(+3)	-88.3	-81.5	6.8
RSH(+5)	-93.6	-88.2	5.3

has such combination), a higher ADC resolution must be used (e.g., 24 bits), as well as, adjustable output/input ranges for both the sensors and the ADC to take full advantage of this resolution. In this way, low enough noise floor levels can be achieved so as to allow the detection of these low amplitude harmonics.

Finally, the results show that the proposed methodology allows detecting the fault at an early stage (when the ITF currents are lower than the rated current) and following the evolution of its severity (as the ITF current increases, the amplitude of the homopolar RSHs increases). Future research will address the quantitative correlation of the fault severity (amplitude of the ITF current) with the magnitude of the ITF indicator (homopolar RSHs amplitude).

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